

Themes, Topics, and Structure of Historical Novels in Southern Vietnam in the Early Twentieth Century

Truong Thi Linh

Faculty of Education, Thu Dau Mot University

ABSTRACT: Southern Vietnamese literature in the first half of the 20th century has recently attracted considerable attention from researchers. However, the themes, topics, and structure of historical novels in this period have not received adequate attention. This article uses an analytical-synthetic method to examine the characteristics and features through careful reading of primary (first-published novels) and secondary (later-published novels in anthologies) sources, developing the research problem. The question posed is: are the themes, topics, and structure of historical novels similar to and different from other genres, such as socio-psychological novels, detective novels, and chivalrous novels? This highlights the crucial and pivotal role of works from this period in the development of modern Vietnamese literature.

KEYWORDS: Southern Vietnamese novels, historical novels, themes, topics, and structure

I. INTRODUCTION

The first half of the 20th century was a pivotal period for Vietnamese literature, gradually moving towards a modern, internationally integrated trajectory. Literature during this time broke away from medieval traditions and embraced modernism as Western civilization gained influence. During this period, young people educated in French-Vietnamese schools or abroad had access to world literature. They were no longer satisfied with the classical Chinese episodic novels or medieval Vietnamese *Nôm* poems. They needed works that evoked contemporary life and expressed their feelings. They found love and hope in Western romantic novels; they encountered the realism and descriptive power of Western realist novels... All of this changed their worldview and philosophy of life. Authors of this period, recognizing the needs of the times, learned from Western novelists. They constructed stories with plots, characters, dialogue, and everyday language. Furthermore, they arranged the stories in a structured order, deliberately building a narrative to attract readers, rather than following the chronological order of episodic novels or the linear timeline of classical Eastern novels. Literary life in Southern Vietnam during the first half of the 20th century was vibrant, with hundreds of newspapers and numerous publishing houses. Each newspaper published a wide range of works (novels, short stories, poetry, travelogues, biographies of famous people, etc.) to attract readers.

However, due to the circumstances of the wars in the late 19th and late 20th centuries (nearly 100 years of French rule and over 20 years of American intervention until 1975), research on Southern Vietnamese literature still has many gaps, especially during the war years. In recent years, research and surveys on Southern Vietnamese journalistic literature have been vigorously pursued, and almost all research topics have been explored in depth. Major Southern Vietnamese authors are mentioned in several key works (Bang Giang, 1974, 1992; Dong Ho, 1970; Doan Le Giang, 2011). The contributions of this period's literature are highly regarded, as the starting point for literary modernization (Le Giang, 2011; Tran Van Giau, 1988; Dong Ho, 1970...). The authors affirm the contributions of early Southern Vietnamese writers to the modernization of Vietnamese literature through their pioneering achievements:

“Truong Vinh Ky - a cultural figure, the first writer of Vietnamese-language chronicles; Nguyen Trong Quan - the first novelist in Vietnamese; Truong Minh Ky - the first translator of French literature; Huynh Tinh Cua - a pioneering writer of Vietnamese-language literature; Tran Chanh Chieu - a reformist writer; Luong Khac Ninh - a reformist poet and journalist; Ho Bieu Chanh - a masterful social and moral novelist; then Truong Duy Toan - a writer of historical and martial arts fiction; Le Hoang Muu - a pioneering and bold novelist; Nguyen Chanh Sat - a renowned martial arts novelist and translator of Chinese stories...”. (Doan Le Giang, 2011, p. 19).

In addition, there are articles, essays, dissertations, and research papers surveying authors, works, literary movements, or literary trends. However, these works either do not or rarely address the themes, topics, and structure of the socio-psychological novel genre in Southern Vietnam during the first half of the 20th century.

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2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article uses statistical methods to classify the characteristics of historical novels in terms of theme, subject matter, and structure. The analytical and synthetic method is also used to analyze and present the research results.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1. Concept of Historical Novel

The Britannica Dictionary defines a historical novel as a type of novel that:

"a novel that has as its setting a period of history and that attempts to convey the spirit, manners, and social conditions of a past age with realistic detail and fidelity (which is in some cases only apparent fidelity) to historical fact. The work may deal with actual historical figures, as does Robert Graves's *I, Claudius* (1934), or it may contain a mixture of fictional and historical characters." (Historical Novel, n.d).

This concept is somewhat similar to the concept expressed in *The Dictionary of Literary Terms*. *The Dictionary of Literary Terms* does not have a separate concept of historical novels but considers them to belong to the genre of historical literature. The genre of historical literature is "works written on historical themes that contain fictional characters and details; however, the real characters and main events are created based on authentic historical sources, respecting the language, clothing, customs and traditions appropriate to that historical period." (Le Ba Han, Tran Dinh Su & Nguyen Khac Phi, 1999, p. 255).

The Dictionary of Literature (new edition) defines historical novels as "a type of novel or fictional narrative work that takes historical themes as its main content" (Do Duc Hieu, Nguyen Hue Chi, Phung Van Tuu and Tran Huu Ta, 2004, p. 1725). This concept is quite general. Tran Nghia (1997) argues that:

"Historical novels, also called "historical narratives," include many works written about historical themes through the description of characters and events, artistically recreating the social appearance and development trends of a historical period, aiming to provide readers with useful inspirations and literary aesthetics. In terms of writing style, on the one hand, it must rely on history when describing characters and events primarily to achieve historical authenticity, but on the other hand, it still allows fiction to an appropriate extent, in order to develop imagination and elevate historical authenticity into artistic authenticity." (Tran Nghia, 1997).

Based on the above opinions, in our view, historical novels are a type of novel that reuses historical figures, events, customs, and lifestyles of a bygone era to educate patriotism and national pride among the people during pivotal/important periods of the country's history. Or, as Goncourt said, "history is a finished novel, a novel is history that could unfold that way" and "God can no longer do anything with history, but man can still write history and reshape it" (as quoted in Phan Cu De, 2006, p. 174).

3.2. Themes

According to Nguyen Van Dan (2012), there are three main types of historical novels in Vietnamese literature: first, objective chapter-act novels; second, educational historical novels; and thirdly, interpretive historical novels. Through the study of historical novels in Southern Vietnam in the early 20th century, we found that educational historical novels almost dominated historical novels in Southern Vietnam in the early 20th century. This type of novel focuses mainly on themes of educating consciousness, patriotism, and national pride. Specifically:

Firstly, the themes express national pride by recreating historical images of national heroes who made great contributions to the country. They are depicted from a personal perspective with "their thoughts, anxieties, worries, joys, sorrows, anger, and small personal aspirations." (Bui Van Loi, 2018, p. 95). They may be figures who established a dynasty, ushering in a new era for the country, such as: Ngo Quyen in *Nam Cuc Tinh Huy* (Ho Bieu Chanh, 1924); Le Loi in *Viet Nam Le Thai To* (Nguyen Chanh Sat, 1929); King Gia Long in the trilogy of novels *Gia Long Tau Quoc* (1930), *Hoang Tu Canh Nhu Tay* (1931), *Gia Long Phuc Quoc* (1932) (Tan Dan Tu); the story of Ly Cong Uan in *Le Trieu Ly Thi* (Pham Minh Kien, 1931)... They may also be a general with illustrious military achievements, such as: Ly Thuong Kiet in *Viet Nam Ly Thuong Kiet* (or *Viet Nam Ly Trung Hung* - Pham Minh Kien, 1929); Nguyen Trai in *Lieu than vi nuoc* (Nguyen Y Buu, 1930)... Sometimes they are fictional heroes such as: Vo Dong So in *Giot mau chung tinh* (Tan Dan Tu, 1926), Ly Phung Tien in *Viet Nam anh kiet* (Pham Minh Kien, 1928), Thanh Tong in *Nang ganh cang thuong* (Ho Bieu Chanh, 1930)... Although a character based on adaptations, Thanh Tong (a character created from Pierre Corneille's *Le Cid*) possesses the essence, personality, way of thinking, actions, gestures, attitude, and language... all imbued with a strong Vietnamese spirit: such as patriotism, family pride, and especially, he highly values love. This could be a romantic trait stemming from the talented Confucian scholars in medieval Vietnamese literature such as Kim Trong and Tu Hai (in *The Tale of Kieu* - Nguyen Du).

Historically, Ngo Quyen was a talented general, skilled in military command, winning hearts and minds, and organizing battles that brought prestige to his dynasty, striking fear into the hearts of his enemies. However, in *Nam Cuc Tinh Huy* (Ho Bieu Chanh), we see a hero depicted with everyday worries and anxieties, with personal goals of revenge: for example, the military campaign aimed at avenging Kieu Cong Tien for killing his father-in-law, Duong Dinh Nghe. Ngo Quyen is portrayed with the thoughts and concerns of a far-sighted individual, capable of predicting the future based on the facts before him. For instance, he laments to his

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wife, Duong Phu Nhan: "I am saddened by many things, saddened by matters of home and country, worried about the heavy burdens of gratitude and obligation; it is truly difficult to express everything to my wife." (Ho Bieu Chanh, 1924, p. 2). And he confides his feelings to his wife:

"I was born into a humble family; unfortunately, my parents died early, so I had to wander the world from Duong Lam. I intended to find kindred spirits to form a brotherhood with, to establish some reputation and honor as a man (...) I had no talent, yet my father-in-law married his girl to me. Then, during the uprising to fight Ly Khac Chanh and drive Ly Tan back to China, I had little merit; my father-in-law held the position of Military Commissioner, he appointed me to the position of Governor of Ai Chau, responsible for protecting the southern border." (Ho Bieu Chanh, 1924, p. 3).

Such thoughts and feelings of the characters do not exist in official history. This can only be depicted by novelists through the characters' thoughts and feelings about human affairs, the state of the world, and the fate of the nation. Therefore, Bui Van Loi (2018) made a very insightful observation about historical novels, highlighting "the thoughts, anxieties, worries, joys, sorrows, anger, and small personal aspirations" (Bui Van Loi, 2018, p. 95) of the characters.

Secondly, the subject conveys historical values through historical figures and events that greatly influenced the nation and its people, such as the formation of a dynasty, the development and maintenance of national borders, or the expansion of territorial borders... and through this, subtly educates the will for national independence, self-reliance, and self-strengthening. This is mentioned by the authors in the preface when publishing the book. In the "Preface" when publishing *Gia Long tau quoc*, provincial governor Tran Van Tan wrote: "Read national history, read national history, that is the voice of contemporary intellectuals, constantly lamenting with our people." (Tan Dan Tu, 1930, p. 1). Nguyen Tu Thuc, in the "Preface," wrote that as a person of Nam Viet, one must know the past and the present to "filter out a part of the essential essence (...) to nourish the spirit, cultivate integrity (...) then society can hope to rely on them" (Tan Dan Tu, 1930, p. 9). Tan Dan Tu (1930) himself, in the "Author's Preface," also clearly stated his concept when writing novels:

"General history only summarizes the major events, without detailing the minor ones. Historical fiction, however, tells the whole story, both major and minor events, presenting them as a natural scene, vividly before our eyes. General history mentions people, mountains, and rivers, the rise and fall of nations, but it doesn't reveal the nuances of language, emotions, or landscapes. Historical fiction, on the other hand, reveals the characters, mountains and rivers, emotions, language, joy, anger, love, hatred, intellect, spirit, and even the scenery of grass and flowers, houses and palaces, branches, birds, wind, leaves, the music of streams and cicadas. As readers sit and read the book, they feel as if they have transformed into a traveler, seeing a particular landscape or character, making it easy for them to feel the emotions and form the concepts in their minds." (Tan Dan Tu, 1930, p. 14).

Furthermore, the authors' purpose in writing historical novels is to popularize national history, or "national history is becoming more widely known" (Nguyen Chanh Sat, 2015, p. 14), to "commemorate the achievements in expanding the territory and the patriotic devotion of our ancestors." (Nguyen Chanh Sat, 2015, p. 14).

Thirdly, besides praising the heroic deeds of historical figures and important historical events, historical novels of this period also highlight the reality and explain the reasons for the shaky foundations of a dynasty. These reasons stem from the indulgence in pleasure and hedonism, the neglect of the country's fate and the people's well-being, and the incompetence of incompetent rulers like Le Long Dinh (*Tien Le van Mat* - Pham Minh Kien, 1932).

In the "Preface" when publishing the book, author Pham Minh Kien (1932) stated that the book was a good lesson about the immoral and depraved lifestyle of King Le Long Dinh for readers to "stay away from":

"This is the story of King Long Dinh. His actions and gestures were no less than those of Jie and Zhou of China (...) The author found the story very good, and it can be used as a lesson about immoral and depraved lifestyles for readers to avoid." (Pham Minh Kien, 1932, p. 1).

The author describes King Le Long Dinh as: "a lecherous worm, a demon of wine and women, infatuated with beauty, intoxicated by wine, regardless of right or wrong" (Pham Minh Kien, 1932, p. 2). He and Trinh Vuong Phi "spent day and night in the palace, drinking wine, tea, singing, laughing, and caressing, no different from Dat Ky and Tru Vuong in the Shang Dynasty!" (Pham Minh Kien, 193, p. 2). The author even recounts the story of Long Dinh cutting off the leg of a palace maid for accidentally stepping on Trinh Vuong Phi's fan without batting an eyelid.

The purpose of novels of this type is to prevent similar incidents from happening again and to help people and readers understand the laws of history, so they can see them and avoid them. Because the history of a dynasty, of a person's life, can have periods of prosperity and decline, rise and fall... This is a painful lesson that our ancestors have left for future generations. Through this, we aim to educate patriotism, love for the people, concern for the people's lives, protection of borders and territory, the ability to use people wisely, and foresight... so that we can lead the country forward, the dynasty to glory, and the people to a strong nation. As Nguyen Trai said, "The people can propel the boat, and the people can also overturn it," or as President Ho Chi Minh said, "A hundred times easier without the people, nothing can be achieved; a thousand times harder with the people, everything can be accomplished."

The three themes above are the main themes in historical novels of Southern Vietnam in the early 20th century. However, through historical novels of this period, we also see other themes: such as the customs, traditions, lifestyles, and ways of life of the people;

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the themes of corrupt officials and incompetent rulers who only know how to indulge in pleasure and fill their pockets to satisfy their insatiable desires; and the themes of love between young couples in precarious situations, amidst family feuds (such as the ill-fated love of Vo Dong So and Bach Thu Ha in the novel *Giot mau chung tinh* (Tan Dan Tu, 1926), Thanh Tong and Le Bich in *Nang ganh cang thuong* (Ho Bieu Chanh, 1930)...

3.3. Topics

According to Trieu Duong (1964), the theme in historical novels is not just "presenting the biography of a famous person or recounting the developments of a historical phenomenon or event" (Trieu Duong, 1964, p. 52), its theme can be complex, encompassing the values of life "that the author conveys in the work" (Trieu Duong, 1964, p. 52). In addition, through historical novels, readers can discover more "interpretations of some events of the past, pictures of customs and traditions" (Trieu Duong, 1964, p. 53). Furthermore, historical novels must help readers discover and solve "essential human problems, focusing on portraying people with their rich lives and souls." (Trieu Duong, 1964, p. 53). This requirement reflects a reality: historical novels not only reconstruct customs and traditions in history, but also address and guide readers in solving the political and historical problems they are facing in their time. We completely agree with this view of Trieu Duong (1964).

Firstly, the theme of praising national historical heroes aims to educate national self-reliance through several novels: Ngo Quyen in *Nam Cuc Tinh Huy* (Ho Bieu Chanh, 1924); Le Loi in *Vietnam Le Thai To* (Nguyen Chanh Sat, 1929); Ly Thuong Kiet (*Vietnam Ly Thuong Kiet/Ly Trung Hung* - Pham Minh Kien, 1929); Nguyen Trai (*Lieu Than Vi Nuoc* - Nguyen Y Bui, 1930); Gia Long (*Gia Long Tau Quoc* (1930), *Hoang Tu Canh Nhu Tay* (1931), *Gia Long Phuc Quoc* (1932) - Tan Dan Tu); *Le Trieu Ly Thi* (Pham Minh Kien, 1931)...

While studying several historical novels by Nguyen Chanh Sat, Tan Dan Tu, Ho Bieu Chanh, Pham Minh Kien, etc., we noticed that most authors always praise the indomitable and heroic spirit of the heroes in battle: scenes of them going to the battlefield, scenes of them rallying their soldiers, close-ups of their thoughts and anxieties during the process of conquering history... are all described in detail, specifically, and meticulously: from their demeanor, gestures, attitudes, behavior, thoughts... everything is expressed very vividly. The characters all show an indomitable, heroic, courageous, and valiant spirit... Most of the novels record the imprint of those who started a dynasty or the heroic figures in the nation's history.

Secondly, the theme of criticizing those who abuse their power to exploit and oppress the people, to enjoy life excessively without worrying about material needs or protecting national sovereignty, such as Le Long Dinh in *Tien Le van Mat* (Pham Minh Kien, 1932); some officials, because they were proud of having contributed much to the court, abused their power, either through corruption or by exceeding the king's authority and the law in handling both public and private affairs, such as Vo Thanh Nhon and Bui Khac Phu (*Gia Long tau quoc* - Tan Dan Tu)...

Thirdly, the theme of avenging one's father in some novels adapted from this period: through the narrative poem *Vay moi phai* and the novel *Nang ganh cang thuong* by Ho Bieu Chanh (adapted from Pierre Corneille's play "Le Cid"), it shifts to a larger theme: protecting the homeland, the country, its people, customs, and traditional practices. Through historical novels, readers can see more than just characters and events, but also address modern issues. This point was also raised by Phuong Luu when commenting on W. Shakespeare's Hamlet: "From the theme of avenging his father in a lost play, Shakespeare in Hamlet shifted to the theme of recognizing the evil state of society and the consciousness of fighting to reform it..." (Phuong Luu (editor-in-chief) et al., 1997, p. 263). This is perhaps true in the case of studying some historical novels such as *Nang ganh cang thuong* (Ho Bieu Chanh, 1930), *Tien Le van Mat* (Pham Minh Kien, 1932)...

Fourthly, through historical novels praising heroes who sacrificed themselves for a great cause, such as Thanh Tong in *Nang ganh cang thuong* (Ho Bieu Chanh), Ho Canh Xuan (*Viet Nam anh kiet, Vi nghia lieu minh* - Pham Minh Kien, 1926)...

Fifthly, besides praising national heroes, the author does not forget to criticize weak and decadent kings like King Le Long Dinh (*Tien Le van Mat* - Pham Minh Kien, 1932) because, according to the author's opinion: "His actions and gestures were no less than those of Jie and Zhou of China... The author finds the story very interesting, and it can be used as a path to debauchery and immorality for viewers to avoid..." (Pham Minh Kien, 1932, p. 1) - This theme is rarely seen - and if it is, it is mainly for educational purposes: educating the people not to follow in the footsteps of those who came before. The purpose of writing this novel was to distance oneself from, rather than to depict, the irreparable bankruptcy of the feudal regime, as Phuong Luu (1997) said when discussing the theme of the works *The "True Story of Ah Q"* (Lu Xun) shows a "spiritual legacy of a decaying, weak feudal ideology affecting all classes of people..." (Phuong Luu (editor-in-chief) et al, 1997, p. 264).

3.4. Structures

The structure of historical novels does not differ significantly from the structure of other genres. However, we observe that in most historical novels, authors mostly use traditional structures (chapters, linear chronological order, circular structure...), while modern structures (story within a story, character arcs, simultaneous narratives, open structure, etc.) are less frequently used in this genre.

Firstly, historical novels in Southern Vietnam during the early 20th century commonly used a structure based on a universal model (Nguyen Thanh Thi, 2014). This model includes: I. The appearance of a historical figure in a particular context. This context

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could be the arduous journey of King Gia Long to escape the pursuit of the Tay Son army in *Gia Long Tàu Quốc* (Tan Dan Tu); it could be the sleepless nights of Ngo Quyen contemplating the fate of the nation in *Nam Cuc Tinh Huy* (Ho Bieu Chanh); The nation's fate in turmoil when Le Loi raised an army in *Vietnam Le Thai To* (Pham Minh Kien)... II. The resistance struggle endured hardships, suffering, and losses of human and material resources, but never retreated. In *Nam Cuc Tinh Huy* (Ho Bieu Chanh), Ngo Quyen led his troops to suppress Kieu Cong Tien because he had killed and usurped the power of the Military Governor Duong Dien Nghe, Ngo Quyen's father-in-law. Following this, he ordered his generals to block the advance of the Han army and achieved a resounding victory on the Bach Dang River. III. The result was the pacification of the country and its reunification. In *Gia Long Phuc Quoc* (Tan Dan Tu), King Gia Long ascended the throne, ushering in a period of peace and prosperity. In *Vietnam Le Thai To* (Pham Minh Kien), Le Loi ascended the throne and fairly rewarded and punished his meritorious officials.

Secondly, the parallel narrative structure is common in historical novels. In *Nam Cuc Tinh Huy* (Ho Bieu Chanh), the first narrative thread concerns Ngo Quyen and his generals' planning and strategy to defeat Kieu Cong Tien. The second narrative thread concerns Kieu Cong Tien's troop deployment. The third narrative thread concerns the Nam Han army's impending invasion of the country. All three narrative threads ultimately converge on Ngo Quyen's punishment of Kieu Cong Tien, defeating the Southern Han invaders, pacifying the country, unifying the land, and ascending to the throne.

Thirdly, the contrasting structure between two lines of characters—good and evil, righteous and wicked, greedy and virtuous—is also quite common in historical novels. We can see this type of structure in several historical novels by Ho Bieu Chanh, Tan Dan Tu, Pham Minh Kien, and others.

Fourthly, the linear chronological narrative structure is almost exclusively used in historical novels. In this structure, events that happened first are told first, and those that happened later are told later. Characters rarely reminisce or reflect on the past or the future. They always follow a straight line, never hesitating between choosing a direction to go next. For example, Thanh Tong (in *Nang ganh cang thuong* by Hồ Biểu Chánh), upon hearing that his father had been beaten and humiliated by the Grand Marshal Lê Niệm, his father-in-law, in the royal court, immediately went to his house to inquire about the matter, despite his own pain and suffering. When the king ordered him to lead the army to victory and return victorious, he would be pardoned for killing a court official and granted his marriage to Lê Bích (Lê Niệm's daughter). Thanh Tông obeyed and left immediately. Upon returning victorious, the king arranged a marriage between Thanh Tong and the princess (because Le Bich had run away, unwilling to marry the man who had killed her father). Thanh Tong defied the king's and his father's orders, determined to find Le Bich. Ultimately, through his unwavering resolve, he found Le Bich, saved the king, and lived happily ever after.

In summary, the structure of historical novels largely leans towards traditional forms such as: chapter structure, linear narrative structure, two opposing character lines structure, and a universal model structure (consisting of three parts)... In the chapter structure, numbering sometimes uses Roman numerals, and sometimes uses "chapter number". However, after the chapter number, there are always two verses introducing the chapter's content. This is clearly demonstrated in: in *Vietnam Le Thai To*, "Chapter thirteen. Taking Nghe An, Le Loi proclaimed himself king,/ lost the fortress, Cam Bang lost his life." (Nguyen Chanh Sat, 2015, p. 226); or in *Vietnam anh kiệt*, "I. Ho Canh Xuan explained his suffering,/ Ly Phung Tien was moved with compassion." (Pham Minh Kien, 2015, p. 3).

Furthermore, the authors also employ modern structural techniques such as character-based narrative structure, parallel structure, etc. This type of structure allows both the author and the reader to follow their favorite characters, while simultaneously allowing them to imagine multiple events and scenes occurring consecutively at the same time. This prevents the reader from becoming bored, creating a continuous thread running through the story, helping the reader visualize the entire narrative clearly and transparently. All of this is thanks to the meticulous arrangement and innovative art of plot construction by the authors, influenced by Western-style novels.

However, we have observed that most historical novels from this period feature, to varying degrees, a deep and passionate love affair between the main male and female characters, or at least a significant one, in the development of the plot. Most love stories in historical novels are traditional in nature: they love the talent, beauty, thoughts, morals, and lifestyle of their beloved. They may wait for their partner with unwavering faith, like Ngoc Suong waiting for Chau Van Tiep in *Gia Long's Escape from the Country* (Tan Dan Tu); they may confide all their worries and thoughts to their spouse, like Ngo Quyen with Duong Phu Nhan in Ho Bieu Chanh's *Nam Cuc Tinh Huy*; they may wait in vain for a passionate love that is burdened by the revenge for their father's murder, like Thanh Tong and... in *The Heavy Burden of Moral Conduct* (Ho Bieu Chanh)...

4. CONCLUSIONS

Examining the themes, topics, and structure of historical novels in Southern Vietnam during the first half of the 20th century, it can be seen that this is an important genre in the modernization process of Vietnamese literature. Authors not only aimed to recreate history as a system of past events, but also used it to express national consciousness, patriotism, and the aspiration to affirm cultural identity in the context of a turbulent colonial society. Historical novels, therefore, served both as documentary material and as an artistic space for writers to convey their conceptions of the nation, its people, and its era.

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In terms of themes and topics, historical novels in Southern Vietnam during this period often focused on historical figures, uprisings against foreign invaders, and important events in national history, while simultaneously honoring chivalry, loyalty, and community spirit. Through these works, they contributed to arousing national pride and strengthening historical awareness among contemporary readers. Besides historical elements, many works also intertwine moral, personal, and social aspects, creating a humanistic depth to the themes.

In terms of structure, historical novels in Southern Vietnam during the first half of the 20th century show a combination of traditional narrative models and elements of modern novels. The structure often develops along a historical event line combined with a central character line, while employing various techniques such as interweaving flashbacks, weaving in side stories, or combining historical data with artistic fiction. This flexibility helped the works maintain historical accuracy while enhancing the narrative's appeal.

In general, historical novels in Southern Vietnam during the first half of the 20th century not only reflected the historical awareness of contemporary intellectuals and writers but also contributed to laying the foundation for the later development of Vietnamese historical novels. Studying the themes, subjects, and structure of these works therefore not only helps to identify the poetic characteristics of a literary period, but also clarifies the role of literature in constructing historical memory and nurturing national consciousness in the spiritual life of society.

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